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THE ROLE OF OIL IN THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE PEARL OF THE CASPIAN SEA - BAKU

Abbasova M.

Ph.D. Prof.

Azerbaijan University of Languages

Abstract

This article provides information about the emergence and development of the city of Baku. It is emphasized here that this settlement on the Absheron Peninsula arose in ancient times. The growth and development of the city was facilitated by the presence of oil, salt and its location in a convenient bay of the Caspian Sea. In the early Middle Ages, the Arabs made a great contribution to the study of the Caspian Sea and the surrounding lands. Later European travelers described Baku as a major port on the Caspian Sea. Since Baku played a big role in trade between eastern countries and Europe. It should be noted that all researchers and travelers were especially interested in the presence of oil on Absheron.

The second half of the article states that the development of the oil industry contributed to the influx of foreign capital into Baku, at the forefront of which were the famous Nobel brothers. All innovations related to the development and processing of the oil industry were introduced in Baku. This is the first well in the world, the production of kerosene, the transportation of oil by sea by tankers, and even the extraction of oil from the bottom of the sea already in the 20th century, i.e. in 1949.

Keywords: Baku, oil, Caspian Sea, kerosene, tanker transportation, Nobel brothers.

Situated on the seashore, Baku had many advantages. Firstly, the sea was the decoration of the city; the people living here connected their lives with the sea. Since ancient times, the city's inhabitants, associated with the sea, have been good sailors and fishermen. Using sea routes, they had access to Europe, Asia and the Maghreb countries. Merchants and sailors also arrived from these countries to the shores of the Caspian Sea.

Many paleontological, archaeological, numismatic and written sources indicate that settlements arose on Absheron and on the site of present-day Baku in ancient times.

The small settlement of Baku in a well-protected bay is gradually turning into a feudal city [9, p.246].

Baku was first mentioned in sources of the 5th century. The Byzantine author Priscus of Pania, describing the route from Scythia to Media, writes that near the settlement of Baku "a flame blazes from sea stone," i.e. the lights are burning. The great popularity of Baku in the early Middle Ages outside the region was associated with the oil produced nearby, which was already being exported. It was used not only for lighting, but also for military purposes and as a healing agent. Baku was also known for its salt mines, as well as a convenient harbor [6, p.197].

For the period from the 7th to the 10th centuries, there is rare information about Baku. After the Arabs conquered the territory of Azerbaijan, the name of the city, as S. Ashurbeyli writes, changed from "Bagu" or "Baguvan" to "Baku". The Arab geographer al-Istarkhi reports that fire worshippers lived not far from Baku [4, p.96].

It is known that back in the 8th century, and the beginning of the 9th century. Baku was not among the large shopping centers. This is confirmed in the written sources of Arab geographers and historians, who call Baku a small but developed feudal city. Al-Balazuri's book "The Book of the Conquest of Countries" reports

that in the second half of the 8th century, the ruler of Derbent sent for the tax "to the oil and salt producers in Shirvan" [8, p.89].

The importance of Baku as a convenient harbor increased in the 11th-15th centuries. Since trade exchanges took place between countries located on the coast of the Caspian Sea. The items of trade were: oil and salt, madder and silk, which were exported to different countries both by sea from Baku (in the south) and the village of Bilgya (in the north), and by land [6, p. 224].

In the 12th century. The importance of Baku as one of the rich cities on the Caspian Sea and a trading center is noted in the famous qasida of the poet Khagani (12th century), praising Shirvanshah Akhsitan.

Large ancient routes of world international transit trade between the countries of the East and the West, running through Azerbaijan, passed near the Absheron Peninsula.

Arab geographer of the 10th century. Masudi in his work "Gold Copies and Mines of Gems" writes: "In Baku there are sources of white and other types of oil. And no in the world - God knows well! - there is no white oil anywhere except this place, and it is the coast of the Shirvan kingdom. In these oil-bearing lands there is a volcano, or a source of fire, constantly spewing flames upward all the time" [8, p.95].

Another Arab geographer Al-Istakhri, in his treatise "The Book of the Ways of States," says about Baku that it is a city in which there are sources of white and dark gray oil. Caravans from all over the Middle East arrived here for oil. Slavic, Khazar, Venetian, Byzantine, Chinese, Iraqi, Syrian, Kentish, Iranian, and Indian merchants came to Baku. Baku, located at the crossroads of trade routes, has always been the focus of attention of foreign invaders who fought for influence in the region [13, p. 74].

The international trade relations of Azerbaijan are evidenced by the finds of various coin treasures and coins found both on the territory of Baku and in other cities that participated in the trade.

Sources report that in the XII-XV centuries. Azerbaijani cities received silk, silk fabrics and “gold-woven Chinese brocade” from China, which were worth almost their weight in gold, as well as other goods. Among them, expensive porcelain ware occupied an important place.

The importance of Baku as an important port is noted in an ancient atlas compiled in 1375 in the Catalan language. Here the Caspian Sea is called the Baku Sea and the Sarah Sea.

Near the port of Baku, Cape Preala is marked on the map, in which it is not difficult to recognize the island of Pirallahi. Further indicated Barmachu, i.e. Mountain (Barmak) Barmak and nearby Hamau, possibly Shamakhi. As we can see, the Catalans were known as good sailors, they sailed in the Caspian Sea for trade purposes and they were well aware of the entire coast of the Caspian Sea and the city of Baku [6, p.213].

At the end of the XIII and beginning of the XIV centuries. Iran and Azerbaijan's international trade with the Far East and other countries is expanding significantly. Maritime trade along the Caspian Sea is gaining great development. There is information that the Genoese and Venetian merchants, whose ships sailed on the Black Sea, also had their own fleet in the Caspian Sea, on the shores of which they founded their trading posts. The Venetian traveler Marco Polo, who visited Iran and the southern regions of Azerbaijan around 1293, reports that only by this time the Genoese began to travel along the Caspian Sea, bringing silk called gelli (Gilyan).

An anonymous geographical work in Persian, written in the 20s of the 13th century, says about Baku: “This is a city in the Shirvan region on the seashore. All night his land burns like fire; They put a cauldron on it and the water on the ground boils. His goods: black, white, green oil and salt” [1, p.143].

Information about Baku oil is also found in the reports of such geographers as Yakut Hamavi (who wrote around 1227) and Zakaria Kazvini (his work dates back to 1275).

In subsequent times, thanks to the reports of travelers, merchants and missionaries, much became known about the life, economy, trade and diplomatic relations, and traditions of the inhabitants of the city of Baku. In their drawings and memoirs they provide interesting information.

In the XIII-XIV centuries. During the period of prosperity of Baku, as the capital of the state of the Shirvanshahs, they owned a strong fleet, which consisted of several dozen ships. The importance of Baku at this time increased as one of the fortified cities and an important port on the Caspian Sea. Back in the Middle Ages (X-XIII centuries), in order to defend the Caspian coast from frequent attacks from the sea, a military fleet was created in the state of the Shirvanshahs and powerful naval fortifications were erected in Baku. The navy of the Shirvanshah state played an important role in protecting the coast. The merchants who sailed their ships to the shores of the Caspian Sea were well aware of the wealth of these regions of Azerbaijan. Ancient

Scandinavian treatises and maps of the 12th-14th centuries, compiled on the basis of the practical experience of the Vikings, contain a lot of information about Albania and the Caspian (Girgan) Sea. The main military-political force that resisted aggression from the north was the state of the Shirvanshahs, which had a fairly strong military system, which included both ground forces and naval forces. In general, the military organization of the Shirvan state had a rather complex structure, since military affairs here had a centuries-old tradition, rooted in ancient Albania.

By the end of the 12th and beginning of the 13th centuries, the Shirvanshahs' fleet fully met the requirements of its time and was able to fulfill all the tasks assigned to it to protect the coast and merchant shipping. In chronicle sources one encounters the naval terminology of the Shirvanshahs' fleet, which was created on an Arabic basis. The so-called marine encyclopedia of Ahmed ibn Majid describes maritime terms used in the Mediterranean, Caspian and Red Seas. The ships of the Shirvanshahs' fleet used such navigational instruments as a water clock, barometer, astrolabe, and compass. The personnel of the ship were called “mallah” or “bahri” i.e. seafarers. There were high, middle and low compositions of the ship's servants. The highest ranks are the captain on large ships, on small warships “rais”, gunners oil throwers “naffat”, sailors “navvat” [3, p.132].

In all likelihood, the ships of the Shirvanshahs could only destroy the enemy fleet using missile launchers and incendiary weapons. On the warships of the Shirvan fleet, “charkh” type installations were installed, which threw a lit spear at a distance of 300-500 meters.

After the victory in the 12th century. in 1175, the poet Khagani called the Shirvanshahs over the Russians the admiral, or more precisely “amir al-bahr”, translated as the head of the sea. All the armed forces of the country, including the naval forces, were subordinated to Shirvanshah. The commandant of the Baku port was called “Shah Bender”; his subordination included the personnel servicing the “Manar” lighthouse, etc. [10, p.59]

Thus, from the end of the 13th century. Azerbaijan and the coast of the Caspian Sea began to attract the attention of Europeans, who from that time on visited these places in search of markets for purchasing silk. Gilan and Shamakhi silk become items of international trade. In this regard, the importance of Baku rises as a convenient port on the Caspian Sea, which has grown thanks to transit trade with Shamakhi. Apparently, the Genoese from the end of the 13th century. We have also been to Baku.

The importance of Baku as a port can be seen from the fact that starting from the 14th century. We find in various medieval authors the name “Baku Sea”, which they used to designate the Caspian Sea. For example, the Castilian ambassador Ruy Gonzales de Clavijo mentioned the Baku Sea in his diary in 1404. The Venetians also called it the Baku Sea in their notes. Barbaro (1474) “mare di Bachu”, Contarini (1473) “mare di Bachau”, Anjalello (1509) “mar di Baccue”, etc. [9, p.164]

One of the interesting sources about the history of Baku is a geographical work by a Persian author of the first half of the 14th century, written in 1339-1340. Hamdullah Qazwini, who in his work *Nuzhat al-Kulub* writes very briefly about Baku: "Bakuye belongs to the fifth climate. The climate is close to hot." He mentions 200 islands of the Caspian Sea and calls the most famous of them the island of Abaskun, which was inhabited. Then Hamdullah Qazwini describes the artisanal method of extracting Baku oil: "The greatest deposit is in Bakuya. And there is an area where they dig wells so that (oil) comes out. Oil is on the surface of the water, and it is extracted from those sources" [11, p.191].

In the XIII-XV centuries. Western European travelers began to appear here, who, like Eastern authors, noted large oil production in these places. The famous Venetian traveler of the 13th century. Marco Polo reports on Baku oil springs. Oil was used not only in many sectors of economic life, but also as a medicinal product. The healing properties of oil have been noted since ancient times. A number of diseases were cured with Baku oil. The healing properties of Absheron oil were known far beyond the borders of Azerbaijan and people came here from various and distant countries for treatment: The healing properties of Baku oil were also noted by the Venetian traveler of the second half of the 15th century. Josaphato Barbaro: "In this part of the sea there is another city called Baku, from where the sea was called Baku, near which there is a mountain pouring out black oil, used at night in lamps and for rubbing on camels twice a year, because if they do not rub it in, then they suffer from parasha" [14, p.218].

In addition to the Venetians who provide information about Baku, there is evidence from a native of Baku, an Azerbaijani geographer from the late 14th to early 15th centuries. Abdar-Rashid Bakuvi, who in his work (written in 1403) left an interesting description of the city and about the extraction of oil and salt in Absheron. At the end of the 14th and beginning of the 15th centuries. In Baku there was a water supply and kyagriz (well) system that supplied water to the population of the fortress. Bakuvi notes that its water is extracted from wells and springs dug in rocks, filtered in them, and is very pleasant." These wells were discovered in large numbers on the territory of the Shirvanshahs' palace during archaeological excavations. Next to the palace there was a large reservoir-reservoir, now closed, apparently supplying water to the palace and the nearby bathhouse [5, p.95].

On an old map of the 15th century. discovered in Italy in 1914, Bachi can be made out, designated as an important city on the Caspian Sea. The map was compiled by Dalmatians, who were good sailors and visited Baku and other cities of Azerbaijan [6, p.240].

Somewhat later in the 18th century. caravan trade declined with the advent of bandits who robbed caravans, however, the sea trade route from Astrakhan to Baku still did not lose its importance in international trade. I. Lerch reports that merchants crossed the Caspian Sea to Derbend, Gilan and carried on trade without leaving their ships. The ships stopped besides the Baku harbor and in the strait between the Absheron Peninsula and Pir-Allahi.

In addition to the Baku port, Absheron had the port of Bilgya on the international maritime trade routes of the Caspian Sea. The village of Bilgya juts out into the sea and is located on Cape Amburansky. Finds, reports from authors, trading companies make it clear that there was a port here in the Middle Ages.

An employee of the English trading company Barrow, in letters sent to England, in 1580 gives a message about the cities of Azerbaijan. In particular, he mentions the "Bild" (Bilgya) site near Baku. It is no coincidence that many items of ship equipment were found here during the work of an underwater archaeological expedition [9, p. 136].

Trade advances along the Caspian Sea connected the cities of the Caspian region and other cities of Europe and Asia. During the time of Catherine II, Baku was given attention as a commercial port, which was supposed to serve as a base for supplying Russian troops. To rebuild the Baku port, funds were allocated and craftsmen were sent to equip the port; he wrote to Russia that Baku is the best port on the Caspian Sea, many traders from Iran and the Middle East flock here.

The Venetian traveler who lived at the end of the 15th and beginning of the 16th centuries, Anjalello, calls Baku (Vassie or Baccara) a beautiful harbor on the Caspian Sea, which served as a port for Tabriz. According to Anjalello, Baku "used to be the first place of this sea," after which it is called Bakun [6, p.202].

The Caspian Sea and especially its oil-bearing region continued to interest Europeans, who sent explorers here.

The Caspian Sea was depicted in most detail on the map of Tezigano, compiled in 1367. The Duchess of Parma sent a copy of it to Russia [6, p.205].

On the map of A. Olearius in 1633 (he was the secretary of the embassy sent from the German duchy to the Moscow prince), the Caspian Sea was depicted as a square. The most correct direction of the outlines of the Caspian Sea from north to south was given by the Dutch shipbuilder Jan Strehuys in 1667. In 1700, the cartographer of Louis XIV presented the Caspian Sea on the map in the form of an irregular circle [14, p. 219].

After the conquest of the Caucasus and Northern Azerbaijan by the Russian Empire in the 1st half of the 19th century, the development of the oil industry intensified. In 1948, the first well was drilled in the world; for comparison, let us recall that in the USA the first well was drilled in 1859, i.e. 11 years after Baku. In 1859, the first kerosene plant in the world was built in Baku.

In the 2nd half of the 19th century. The influx of foreign capital began in Baku. The first to arrive were Swedish entrepreneurs, the Nobel brothers. Offices of the Rothschilds (France), Rockefellers (USA) and other entrepreneurs opened.

A steam fleet appeared in the Baku port. Many migrants - Russians, Jews, Germans, Poles, Georgians, Armenians, Iranians, etc. - began to come to Baku. As a result, not only the bourgeoisie, but also the working class became multinational. With the oil boom, cultural life began to flourish, with theaters and other magnificent buildings opening. Baku became known as the "Paris of the Caucasus" [7, p.162].

As is known, Baku oil magnates were largely focused on Europe. They invited famous European architects to Baku and, as if competing with each other, created mansions that perpetuated their names.

Baku was a significant seaport for maritime transport in Russia and occupied one of the first places. In 1873, the world's first oil barge "Alexander", built by the Artemyev brothers, began to operate in the Caspian Sea; with the advent of other oil tankers, the export of oil products increased 50 times [9, p.67].

Speaking about shipbuilders and shipowners of Baku, who have ships on the Caspian Sea, one cannot fail to mention the Nobels. Brothers Robert, Ludwig, Emmanuel acted as a partnership; they created the Branobel enterprise. Thus, the oil tanker "Zoroaster" of 1878 remained in history as the world's first ship of this type. It had a length of 136.5 m and a width of 27.5 m, with a capacity of 15,000 pounds. The partnership owned 13 ships. In 1879 they launched the ship "Bud-dha", in 1882, "Socrates", in 1891 "Robert Nobel", in 1909 "Emmanuel Nobel", then "Moses Spinoza", etc. [2, p.267].

In 1893, the Nobel Brothers Partnership entered into an agreement with the Standard Oil oil company, owned by the American oil magnate Rockefeller.

During this period, local Azerbaijani capitalists played a major role in the development of maritime trade. In particular, the Dadashev family of millionaires. They were the founders of the national bourgeoisie and for the first time, with their light hand, Russian-Persian trade at sea began. They founded the shipbuilding industry in the Caspian Sea, built ship repair factories called "Dock Elling", "Dadashev's Dock". For the first time in Bilgya Gadzhiaga, Dadashev created a home for the elderly at his own dacha. The first major contribution to the architecture of the city, to the construction of eclectic houses using elements of national architecture, was made by this family.

The Dadashev houses became architectural monuments of Baku. An example is the building of the Nizami State Museum - formerly the Metropol Hotel. The Dadashevs received large profits from shipping and had connections with the countries of the Near and Middle East [2, p.91].

Another large company in this industry was the Asadullayev family. Ismail Asadullayev owned both freight and passenger ships, receiving large incomes from the shipping company. There have been cases when ships, at the request of Russia or other countries, were rented to transport goods. Receiving a large income, he kept his savings in 17 European banks. Oil industrialist Shamsi Asadullayev was also from this family. He managed to open a kerosene plant. He was the first local to begin transporting oil across the Caspian Sea. It had a wide network of steamships and a series of oil tankers called "Asia", "Africa", "America". Having created a market, he began to compete with his brothers. Nobels, he was even called "The Thunderstorm of Nobels" [2, p.172]

It is known that the world's first oil tanker was "Zorastr" and it belonged to the company br. Nobel. However, it was not necessary to wait long, and in 1897 Sh. Asadullayev launched 3 oil tankers built by the

English company Armstrong in Newcastle. He was very passionate about his ships, ordered equipment for them, strived for their improvement, for the best design; the composition of the sailors on the ship was uniformly dressed with a certain emblem, monogram.

In Baku Bay in the 2nd half of the 10th century. many ships were moored. In the book "Documents on the History of Baku," which contains archival materials of the 19th century. there is a report from the head of the Baku commercial port, V. Davydov, on the movement of ships and cargo turnover of the port for 1907. The names of Mamed Ali, Mamed Baghira and Alesker Useinovs are mentioned here, who had about 6 ships, mostly cargo ones. They were hereditary shipbuilders with a large cargo turnover. Their ships were built abroad [9, p.162].

If you trace how the size and carrying capacity of ships increased, you can conclude how successfully things were going in Baku. The carrying capacity of the oil tanker fleet in the Caspian Sea has increased. By the end of the 19th century, there were 345 oil tankers, of which 133 were steam and 212 were sailing. By the beginning of the 20th century, 80% of all petroleum products in the world were exported from Baku by sea. This suggests that the Caspian Sea is the ancestor of the world's tanker fleet. The development of maritime transport has turned Baku into a first-class port, in terms of equipment and convenience, which has no competitors on the Caspian coast [9, p. 205].

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